

ISSN: 2319 - 829X

Humanities and Social Science Studies

A Bi-annual Interdisciplinary journal

Vol. 12, Issue 2, No. 19 July – December: 2023

UGC Approved (CARE List) Journal

**Humanities and
Social Science Studies**

UGC Approved (CARE List) Journal

ISSN: 2319-829X

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HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCE STUDIES

ISSN : 2319-829X

Peer-Reviewed, Bi-annual, Interdisciplinary UGC CARE List Journal

2023

Volume : 12

Issue :02, Book No: 19

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MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND ECOFEMINISTIC PERSPECTIVES ON CHITRA BANERJEE DIVAKARUNI'S THE FOREST OF ENCHANTMENTS: AN INTROSPECTION

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Abstract

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni is an award-winning and bestselling author, activist, poet and teacher of creative writing. Her works has been published widely in Magazines and anthologies, and her books have been translated into twenty-nine languages. Divakaruni has penned memorable many works such as *Arranged Marriage*, *The Mistress of Spices*, *The Palace of Illusion*, *The Last Queen*. *The Forest of Enchantments* (2019) is a retelling of the story of Ramayana through Sita's perspective. This research aims to analyze the oppression experienced by the female characters in the novel titled *The Forest of Enchantments*. In this novel, the female characters who have been oppressed by male characters and also by other female characters, who had a Patriarchal mindset. The Present research uses Iris Marion Young's five forms of oppression from Justice and the Politics of Difference for the analyses of the novel *The Forest of Enchantments* taken for the study. This paper aims to analyze the implementations of modern technologies in the era of Ramayana depicted in the novel.

Keywords: Oppression, Patriarchal mindset, Technologies, Nature, Ecofeminist.

Introduction

The Indian Literature consists mostly of oral works. The traditional works of Indian literature is considered to be in the form of chants and prayers. Sanskrit hymns are considered to be the early works of Indian literature. The Prominent literary works in Sanskrit is the *Ramayana and Mahabharata*. Ramayana is the first historical biography produced in India. Other great literary works, which marked the golden era of Indian Literature, include *Ratnavali* by Sri Harshamand, *SvapnaVasavadattam* by Bhaasa, *Mricchakatika* by Shudraka, *Meghdoot* by Kalidasa, and *AbhijanamShakuntalam*.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni stepped into the world in the prosperous year 1956. She received her under graduation in 1976 from the Calcutta University. She came to America in the late 1970's to pursue a master's degree in English at Wright State University in Ohio and Ph.D in English, focusing on the subject Christopher Marlowe from the University of California, Berkeley in 1985. Presently, Chitra Banerjee resides with her spouse and offspring in the city of Sunnyvale in California. Divakaruni explores the literary world as a poet, and serves as a Professor in the Creative Writing Program of Houston University.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni is an enviable, a prolific writer and the write ups of Divakaruni has appeared in more than forty periodicals including Atlantic Monthly and The New Yorker. She has written several full-length books which was translated into Hebrew, Japanese, Dutch and twenty six other languages. Some of Divakaruni's works have been adapted into movies. She has won many awards prominent among them American Book Award, A Pen Josephine, Miles Award, Premier Scanner which is also known as the Italian Nobel Award and A Light of India Award, Houston Literary Award. She helps many educate under privileged children in India through an organization called the Board of *Pratham* for many years.

Chitra Banerjee has penned memorable works of fiction such as *Arranged Marriage: stories* (1995), *The Mistress of Spices* (1997), *Sister of my Heart* (1999), *The Unknown Errors of Our Lives* (2001), *Neela: Victory Song* (2002), *The Vine of Desire* (2002), *The Conch Bearer Book One of the Brotherhood of the Couch* (2003), *Queen of Dreams* (2004), *The Lives of Strangers* (2007), *The Palace of Illusions* (2008), *The Mirror of Fire and Dreaming, Book Two of the Brotherhood of the*

Conch (2009), *One Amazing Thing* (2010), *Oleander Girl* (2013), *Before We Visit the Goddess* (2016), *The Forest of Enchantments* (2019), *The Last Queen* (2021).

The term Eco-feminism was first used by the French feminist, Francoise d' Eaubonne in 1974. The third wave of feminism have moved beyond their immediate looking at the relationship with their surroundings. The concept was further developed by King Ynestra in 1974. Eco-feminism is both an activist and academic movement and it tries and explores the inter linkages between nature and women. The human and the non-human world and try to see the critical connections between the domination of nature and the exploitation of women. Women shared a profound relationship with nature as their lives and everyday chores were intertwined with nature. In today's world the exploitation and destruction caused to the environment is evident. This present research aims at interpreting Divakaruni's *The Forest of Enchantments* from the eco-feminist stand points for which the study has taken Young's five faces of oppression.

The Forest of Enchantment is a thought provoking novel based on Ramayana retold from the perception of Sita. The novel came into the literary world in the year 2019 in the United States of America. It focuses on the story of Sita from her perspective quoting through her voice and stating her grief, her resilience, different meanings of love at different life stages. The protagonist of the book Sita, she is wedded to a loving, diligent and be a justice being man Ram. Sita was kidnapped by Ravan and was saved by her beloved husband Ram.

Sita has to prove her virtue by going through the trial by fire and then she takes up the role of Queen and she is preparing to engage with her children to the world but she is far away from the kingdom. Because some people designed rumors and people didn't believe that Sita was pure just on the basis of these rumors, Ram banished Sita. It is not justified, we know as a leader should take care of their subjects and people, it is an absolutely good thought. A leader should know how to balance his personal life and professional life altogether.

Chitra Banerjee portrays the sufferings of women to balance the freedom of the world which is dominated by the praises of the male. The human shortcomings, feelings and emotions and the faces of living creatures are portrayed excellently with Sita exhibiting the tale of a female who was subjected to pain. She hears Valmiki's Ramayana but she is not happy with the one-sided narrative and she wants the world to know her side of the story and which the author fondly calls *Sitayan*. The book truly showcases all the emotions, the dilemmas and the inner turbulence where Sita goes through at her various life stages.

Sita life has so many challenges and Chitra Banerjee really wanted to show people how Sita deals with these challenges in a very elegant and courageous manner. Women's stories are not just about one woman but they are about the whole community of women. Ramayana is really about Ram but the *Sitayan* is about all of the women in the story. When we accept women as they are with all their human flaws and also accept their particular strength that helps them to deal with everyday life in any tough situations. Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni wanted to celebrate these different ways in which women put up with very challenging situations in everyday life but nobody gives them reward for it. The review of literature was made on the article titled "A Feminist Reading of Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's *The Forest of Enchantments*" by Indrajit Patra (2019). The male chauvinistic ideas are showcased in a distinctive perspective by the researcher using feminism. This paper focuses on inequality in gender roles. The second research titled "Re-imagining Sita in Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's *The Forest of Enchantments*" and it focuses on the character of the Protagonist, Sita. The third research titled "Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's *The Forest of Enchantments*: A Chronicle of Commitment, Disloyalty, Probity and Glory" by Monika Duggal (2022). The main idea of the focus of project is to highlight the bond between Sita, the protagonist, and nature. The research focuses on the forest which serves as prime source for the equality of women in the society. The novel, *The Forest of Enchantments* represented the women character in the epic who are often often misunderstood with some women such as Kaikeyi, Surpankha, Mandodari. The novel is also a

satire on duty, deception, infidelity and esteem. It also talks about the struggles of women to become independent in the world. Divakaruni employs desire and ambition to transform a traditional story into a modern novel. At the end, Sita can be regarded as a multifaceted woman of the modern times. She is a dutiful daughter, productive sister, loving wife, gentle daughter-in-law, lover of nature, healer, skilled warrior, administrator and a strong single mother of two.

When Sita married Ram, she went to Ayodhya in her palanquin. During her journey, she was heart broken to the unkind behavior of the soldiers towards the trees. "This is their home, and we are visitors," I added. We should treat them with deference and not cause them needless pain. Ram's brows drew together in surprise. Clearly, he had never considered that plants feel pain as we do" (Divakaruni 56). Sita was always connected with nature. She wished to have a cordial relationship with nature and its resources such as the forest, the bird nests, the fox-lairs, and the medicinal herbs. She also wished to run barefoot on the grass. "But such things were not allowed to princesses, especially those married into the royal family of Ayodhya" (Divakaruni 57).

Yakshas, Rakshasas, Gandharbas and tribal communities resided in the forest. The forest underwent a massive decline when humans took the rights over indigenous person and exploited forest to fulfill their needs like cultivation and hunting. Rakshasas were the people who owned the place, as an aboriginals they had rights over the forest until humans came and overthrown them. Lakshman and Ram could not trust a Rakshasa because they will turn like a venomous snake and they are worse than snakes because they're devious. Lakshman always says that Rakshasa's not a human's and they could not treated with human courtesy. Sita always thinks that if Rakshasa's were died, their families were left without companion. But Ram says that, if we want to live without any disturbance, we want to kill Rakshasa's as quickly as possible. "The best thing you can do with a Rakshasa is to kill it as quickly as possible" (Divakaruni 151).

Ram says that if we kill the Rakshasa's we will bring peace to the forests and make Rishi's life better enough. Sita professed to Ram that they were visitors to the jungle that had its own rules, rhythm, and beauty. Rakshasa's were the real owners of the forest. They did not accept this idea as they felt that men would never change their minds as they believed in the superiority of their own ways.

Sita loved a golden deer from her childhood days, one day she sensed there was something unusual about the animal. Sita walked towards the beautiful deer with spinach leaves. The deer was pleased at the sight of the leaves but it moved away later feeling scared and uncomfortable. Sita admits this truth to Ram but he did not believe her as Lakshman said that the deer may be a Rakshasa in disguise to spy us. Sita wants to save the deer from its wounded skin and she want to heal the deer with the turmeric paste but the deer escaped from her before she could touch it.

Lakshman insists that instead of saving the deer we should scare it off from the place. Suddenly, he takes his bow and wants to kill the deer but Ram says that better she wants to forget the creature and says that he would get something else instead of this deer. Ram and Lakshman didn't know how to mingle with nature and protect it from the endangerment. They didn't admit women's knowledge too. Further, the selected novel is also analyzed using Young five faces of oppression and the oppression faced by women and nature are studied in this research.

Iris Marion Young, the American Philosopher has received global attention for her views on oppression, theory of democracy and feminist political theory. *Justice and the Politics of Difference* was published in 1990, is a prose text that explores political theory. Young, in chapter II of the text emphasis the five faces of oppression which is taken for the present research.

In today's world, the issue of women's oppression is argued by many researched to discover the number of oppressed women in the world. Women are considered to be inferior men. Women experience oppression due to the disparities in gender roles. The novel has highlighted the oppression faced by women characters. Women are denied of their rights in the society which in turn leads to subjugation or oppression.

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The novel exhibits the forms of oppression that the female characters such as Sita, Mandodari, Keikayi, Ahalya and Kaushalya faced. Oppression refers to the cruelty or injustice done by an individual or a group of people who have dominion over the other group. Iris Marion Young divided oppression into five forms such as exploitation, powerlessness, violence, marginalization and cultural imperialism. The purpose of these five faces of oppression is to show the form of oppression that occurred in the novel *The Forest of Enchantments* by Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni. This novel depicted the oppressed life of an Indian woman.

Young considers exploitation as the form of oppression which occurred due to the authority that an individual expresses to have a profit in life. In *The Forest of Enchantments*, some female characters were not treated fairly and this unfair treatment led to oppression of women. "Yes, because Dasharath took numerous wives-several hundred, if my sources are accurate! Some he married for gain and others for pleasure. There's a great deal of rivalry among his queens, and much vying for his attention"(Divakaruni 48).

The above statement exhibits the sexual oppression that King Dasharath performed towards his wives. Dasharath uses women to have pleasure in life. He treated women as a doll to satisfy his own sexual pleasures. He represented women who use men to meet their sensual desires. The wives served as a servant to the king. He also considered them as an object which had no morals. This incident in the novel proves that women objectification existed in the world. Men tend to exploit women in the world in various ways. Dasharath also represented a powerful social capitalist who is a womanizer. He did not give importance to the feelings of the women.

Young states that powerlessness is state of controlling one's decision and existence in life. In the novel *The Forest of Enchantments*, the female characters also experience powerlessness and oppression in life. They feel powerless to resist the oppression done by their male counterparts. Sita's powerlessness is also discussed in the paragraph below:

"O King of Ayodhya! I address you in this way because you've always placed your role asking ahead of your role as husband. In this court, which has been setup to dispense justice to all citizens, I ask you this, for I've been a citizen of Ayodhya too: Did you act justly when you sent me away to the forest, knowing I was innocent of what gossip-mongers whispered? Were you compassionate, the way a king is meant to be, when you banished me without telling me what you were about to do, without allowing me to defend myself or choose my destiny?" (Divakaruni 356).

Sita was banished from the kingdom without any reason. Sita is badly mistreated by the society. She was exiled to the forest because of the rumors spread in the society. Though Ram knew that Sita was innocent, he believed society's portrayal towards Sita. She was pregnant during her banishment. Though Sita was a queen and has power but she would not do anything against her banishment.

Likewise, nature is also oppressed by human beings. There is an incident this novel, Ram, Sita and Lakshman met many sages during their exile and the sages want them to stay in Panchabati near Godavari River. Ram accepted their words and he wants to settle and make their home until the end of their forest journey. Ram and Lakshman found a place where they want to build their hut using leaves. The place around has natural scenery was mesmerized visuals but Sita warned them not to build up a hut. Because she knew the destruction in the place. But Lakshman doesn't accept it, he only thinks about the sceneries around the place. Sita doesn't argue against him but she wants him to know how nature would destroy when human beings do any kind of misleading things toward it.

Sita knows everything about the nature like why birds are screaming, shouting, crippling. But she knows how to heal the disease and love those things within a fraction of time. Actually, in this place all the birds are creating their nest above the tree because anytime would affect its nest with the flood because of the climatic condition. Flood would come and affects Sita's hut but Sita saved Ram and Lakshman against the ferocious flood created by the nature. Even though nature had power but warns is in any ways to escape from it. But we didn't accept it and changing our attitudes against nature. We always think that we want to destroy the nature and not considering their pain while conquer the nature. But at last, human beings were always failed against nature and always nature won.

Marginalization is also experienced by the women characters in the selected novel *The Forest of Enchantments*. Sita experienced marginalization as she was banished by her husband to the forest. Divakaruni states:

“And then he’d sent me away without even having the courage or the consideration to tell me to my face what he was doing to me and why. Without asking me, his helpmate and queen, what I thought should be done, he’d banished me and his babies, all three of us equally innocent, because he believed that was his duty to his people” (Divakaruni 320).

This incident shows that Sita was marginalized. An individual’s life is irrational. Ram believed in many voices of the people who still doubted Sita’s purity even though Sita was safely burned in the fire. Sita exiled herself in order to maintain the dignity of Ayodhya. Ram knew that Sita was innocent but he was forced to accept the ideas of the society.

Iris Marion Young claims that oppression is the most visible kind of violence. Many women undergo violence and their sufferings seems to be endless because of the society. The violence can be seen in many forms, it can be seen through verbal, physical and psychological. In this novel *The forest of Enchantments*, two types of violence can be seen in the female characters such as physical and verbal violence. Physical violence can be exhibited through victim’s body whereas, verbal violence can be seen in the forms of speech, or through harsh and painful words.

In this novel physical violence, which was imposed by Gautam on his wife Ahalya is an example of oppression.

“Worse, Gautam was equally angry with Ahalya and cursed her too. For betraying her sacred marital vows for the sake of bodily pleasure, she would be turned into stone. Ahalya declared her innocence, pointing out that she was as much a victim of Indra’s trickery as Gautam. But it was too late. The curse was in full force. Already her body was petrifying. All Gautam could do at that point was to promise her that a special being would soon be born, and his pure and powerful touch would rest or her to life” (Divakaruni 130).

The above incident is an example of oppression because Ahalya, wife of Gautam, is naive, Indra who should be blamed for tricking her and raping her but she is punished by her husband for the sin which she never committed. She becomes a victim here, she was even cursed by her husband, the curse cannot also be revoked. This shows that women are not allowed to speak for themselves because of oppression though they are innocent. Indra could have proved her innocence; he holds power to prove her innocence but he refused.

Verbal Violence according to Iris Marion Young states that violence by the perpetrator can injure the psychological condition of the victim or make the victim emotionally disturbed. The verbal violence shows from the sentence. Physical violence is also what she got from Ram, the incident shows when Ram was willing to see his beloved wife dumped herself to the fire. After Sita come to Ayodhya, Ram did not welcoming her. She got some violence from her beloved husband, Ram speaks the cruelest words, denouncing Sita in the loudest way that he can manage, and entered Sita walk into the fire even though he knew that Sita was still loyal to him.

According to Young, cultural imperialism means the domination of a culture over people’s mindset. The incident,

“And if you were not, shouldn’t someone be judging you today? You who care so much about the citizens of Ayodhya, did you think of the impact your actions would have on the women of the city? That men would punish their wives harshly or even discard them for the smallest refractions, saying King Ram did so. Then why shouldn’t I?” (Divakaruni 356).

This shows cultural imperialism. Ram was forced to banish Sita to the forest for eternity believing that Sita would come to the home with another man. “Not a week,” Lakshman said. “The rest of your life. Ram is banishing you from his kingdom” (Divakaruni 313). This banishment rules can be applied to any Indian sub continents such as Pakistan, Bangladesh anywhere in South Asia. It is a practice to disinherit a daughter or to kill her, if she commits sin. The killing of woman is known as honor killing, they considered that as honor to kill a cursed woman by husband.

This shows that Nature is also imperialized by the human beings. Lav and Kush saw a horse belonged to a King, Ram it must be used for Ashwamedha Yagna. The greatest kings perform this function in order to lead a prosperous kingdom. It is one of the cultural rituals created by the sages, that is the horse runs wherever it wants to visit the place, and that castle should accept the horse's master as its lord. If a king does not stop the horse, he could fight with the other army. If the king wins, he keeps the horse with them.

If the king loses in a battle, he becomes a vassal of the horse's master. So, here we could know that in order to capture other's kingdom they used the rituals like horse yagna to demolishing the cultures. Lav and Kush, the yagna horse had travelled all over Bharatvarsha. They do not think that the horse could get tired of travelled a long distance. Lav and Kush gave some fruit, water and grass to the horse. The horse didn't have rest but it should travel without food and water. "We thought he was hungry, so we gave him some fruit and soft new river-grass. He really enjoyed that" (Divakaruni 337). Ram cares about his kingdom and people in Ayodhya but he does not think about the horse who running for his kingdom's prosperous.

In the novel, *The Forest of Enchantments*, there are many initial technologies has been used to denote the starting range of using or knowing the technologies. It was very difficult to have technologies in ancient times but in Ramayana, they have used Pushpak Viman. Ravan got Pushpak from Kubera, it's a flying chariot for him. Pushpak Viman was the best flying chariot in the world because it has many features and identify how the relationship between human and machine. It is one of the best example for Human-Machine Technology.

Pushpak Viman has the capacity to interact with humans. The machine made a purring sound, it will create a different sound and it has the ability to look into our minds. Viman had the power to protect and give comfort to the passenger. It had own room, filled with all the luxuries facilities and for entertainment there was a separate hall made up of crystal with divine musicians, dancers and performers play the drama's with the help of characters. "For entertainment, there were halls of crystal with divine musicians and dancers and performers of plays" (Divakaruni 258).

Most of the people thought that it was a supernatural element but it will helps us to know how the flying chariot looks, how it will function and also it gives an idea for humans to develop the aeroplane for the important purpose but it was developed long years ago. Pushpak Viman was very useful for the kings to do their duty without any inconvenience in their profession. But in the novel, Ravan has misused the technology for his personal use or taking vengeance. He kidnapped Sita and they reached Lanka with the help of Pushpak Viman as soon as possible. Technology has both positive and negative in the side of nature but we could use it with a proper way while developing a technology for human attraction.

In the novel, *The Forest of Enchantments* Chitra Banerjee talks about how Rama and his soliders used a technology to build a bridge towards Lanka with the help of sailing stones. The magical stone was tremendous usage for construct a bridge without using any kind of modern technology. In ancient days, it was very difficult to build a bridge. All the Kings developed and build a bridge with the help of stones and limestone. Because at that time people could not use the modern technologies to build up a bridge, they don't know how to use technologies. But the bridge constructed by the old people was very strong and it was not easy to destroy it.

Rama and his soldiers build a bridge between India to Sri Lanka by using sailing stones, it is unbelievable to build a bridge without using sand, cement and Steels. But it is a truth, to convey or accept it. Some of them see these as allegorical or mythologies elements, while others speculate on ancient technological advancements. It will create an idea for human beings to build a bridge in order to reach the destination very quick or easiest way in the world. And also it will not create any pollution or negative impact to the people.

In this novel, astras, it was a specialized weapon often depicted as arrows, that possess unique powers when invoked with specific mantras. Indrajit was used Naag astra to kill Rama and

Lakshman. "Indrajit called upon the powerful Naag astra. A million poisonous snakes exploded from it and bound Ram and Lakshman in their coils" (Divakaruni 219). Rama used Brahmastra; a powerful weapon often considered as a weapon of last resort due to its immense destructive capacity. "But finally, Ram called on the Brahmastra and killed him" (Divakaruni 223).

Lord Rama and other soldiers used bows and arrows of immense power. Rama and Ravan used arrows to kill one another in the battlefield. Rama used a divine bows and arrows against Ravan and Ravan knows how to destroy the arrows from the Rama. Today, we could see if one country put a bomb to another country means, they will know how to destroy the bomb with the help of technologies. For example, we could say Russian and Ukraine war. Now a days, we are using many modern technologies to develop our civilizations from the basic idea which was given by ancient great epics. It was a great inspiration and it had received advanced technologies from the great warriors. In this generation, people became money minded personality by using modern technologies without accepting natural disasters. We should not misuse the technology for our purposes.

Conclusion

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni being a vibrant writer, her *The Forest of Enchantments* is a retelling of a mythological story, but a portrayal of strong female perspectives. Divakaruni wanted to bring out the complications and nuances; she didn't want to portray Ram's simplistically negative; it was hard for him to exile Sita into the forest. One of the most patriarchal interpretations it rejects the ideas of Ram as a stoic, self-assured man who doesn't need for encouragement. Divakaruni preaches the boundaries of stereotypical male and female attributes.

Sita, as portrayed by Divakaruni, is no longer the weak, subservient woman who questions devotion. In her patience, she is dignified and valiant, and Ram stays honourable, serious, and dedicated to his wife. The novel reflects twenty-first-century trends to re-tell stories, situations, and explore modern-day challenges by moving beyond the anger and frustration of the marginalised, as seen in earlier-century post-colonial texts, and attempting to draw out the strength of the situation without undermining the negatives. This book arrives at a critical point in the history of femininity and womanhood because it defines what it is to be a woman. It provides a glimpse into the multifaceted realm of femininity.

Ram banishes Sita to the wilderness when she is accused of adultery by one of Ayodhya's inept people. She is compelled to give birth to her twins alone and to live in the woods as a single mom. Ram challenges her faithfulness after a long period, when he encounters her again coincidentally, despite all the obstacles in regaining her. Sita summons her mother Bhumi to help her get over Ram, for which the ground, Sita's mother, greets and hugs her. Bhumi (Earth) could not bear witnessing her child being treated unfairly by mankind. Because Sita endured nothing till she was within Bhumi. Nature is the pure essence of love and calm. The mother-daughter connection in the novel *The Forest of Enchantments* accurately depicts this facet of ecofeminism.

According to Young, oppression has divided into five forms namely powerlessness, cultural imperialism, violence, exploitation and marginalization. These forms are practiced by women characters in the particular novel *The Forest of Enchantments*. Exploitation makes the figure of women as a dependent to their husband. Mandodari, Kaushalya and Keikayi consider as slave, they have also know that their beloved husband does not heteroicous and they were never loved. In this novel women characters experienced powerlessness, even the queens in their palace, do not have any opportunity to speak for themselves in the male dominated society.

Powerlessness has often experienced by women characters in the novel like Sita, Ahalya, Mandodari, Kekayi. Sita was marginalized when she was sent it to the forest. Sita experienced verbal violence and physical violence both the male and female characters in the novel. Finally, cultural imperialism had treated women as a servant or slave not only human beings but also animals treated badly for their essence. This research throws light on the presence of oppression chiefly in the male

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 authoritative society, and the issues influenced by the oppression. This study focuses on enriching the oppression faced by the female characters.

The book truly a turmoil and the inner turbulence which Sita goes through at her various stages of life. Sita is an intelligent woman one who approaches the society with a comprehensive questioning mind to the world. In today's modern world, everybody craves for power and therefore oppression is being marginalized. Like Sita, one should stand for oneself especially at the time of adversity and injustice. If not he/she would become the part of the oppressed and live under the control of the other. Many countries like India, Nepal gave importance to both the nature and goddesses have been adored by them and equally important to treat women with respect and dignity that any woman deserve. It is our responsibility to take care of natural environment and one should not earn for power through dominance or exploitation.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's *The Forest of Enchantments* used many technologies by the humans and also with the help of animals. But it was used in a positive way and it helped people to got civilization between them. Pushpak Viman, Astras and build a bridge are the implementations of technological advancements. Now a days, the people started to embezzle the technologies in a negative way in nature. They started to destroy nature with the help of technologies.

The future scope of the novel researched on the post-colonial aspects present in the novel, Chaos theory, how female characters have struggled against oppression in the society, psyche of the women roles can be analyzed through Psychoanalytical theory in the novel.

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